

Atomic, Planetary, and Biological Systems Described Under A Common Idea

By

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Important To Point Out

You can speak of the structure of the solar system even though it changes with time. This is important to understand when I refer to sizes of the Moon and the planets, and their orbital distances.

The whole object of developing a theory for the way planetary systems form is that they meet the following criterion: They predict the Titius-Bode rule for the distribution of the planets; the distribution gives the planetary orbital periods from Newton's Universal Law of Gravitation. The distribution of the planets is chiefly predicted by three factors: The inward forces of gravity from the parent star, the outward pressure gradient from the stellar production of radiation, and the outward inertial forces as a cloud collapses into a flat disc around the central star. These forces separate the flat disc into rings, agglomerations of material, each ring from which a different planet forms at its central distance from the star (it has a thickness). In a theory of planetary formation from a primordial disc, it should predict the Titius-Bode rule for the distribution of planets today, which was the distribution of the rings from which the planets formed.

Abstract

This paper describes planetary systems, atomic systems, and biological systems under one idea, as such it is kind of a theory of everything.

In Part 1 of this paper I show that the system of measuring time we have today, that divides the day into 24 hours and the hours into 60 minutes, and the minutes into 60 seconds, that came to us from the ancient Sumerians, who divided the day into 24 hours, and who gave us the base 60 counting that resulted in our base unit of time, the second, to have the duration it has today, was a choice that happens to coincide with my theory that shows that our Earth/Moon/Sun system and atomic systems have a solution in common of the Schrödinger wave equation with the same base unit of time of 1 second.

The ancient Sumerians were the first to settle down from wandering, following the herds and hunting them with stone spearpoint to invent agriculture, architecture, mathematics, astronomy, and writing. They gave us civilization as we know it today. Since their second came to us from their system of counting and I have found the second to be a base unit and natural constant for our planetary system and atomic systems in common, I think it is reasonable to suggest that perhaps they were given their system of mathematics by ancient Aliens. This is easy to suggest because their writings say they were given their knowledge by "Those who came from above."

Part 2 I have a theory for the star systems, the planets and their suns, wherein such systems are solved with the Schrödinger wave equation that is used to solve atomic systems. The result is that star systems and atomic systems, systems on the macroscales and microscales, are governed by the same underlying principles. It came to pass that this theory indicated an overlap with biological systems indicating that biological life could be part of the same idea. Here I develop that.

Part 3 Our solution of the wave equation for the planets gives the kinetic energy of the Earth from the mass of the Moon orbiting the Earth, but you could formulate based on the Earth orbiting the Sun. This yields one second as a base unit as well.

Part 4 We want to find what the wave equation solutions are for Jupiter and Saturn because they significantly carry the majority of the mass of the solar system and thus should embody most clearly the dynamics of the wave solution to the Solar System.

Part 5 We want to solve a habitable planetary system in general and apply it to another star system. We must include the solution of its moon as well, because the Moon of the Earth makes life optimally possible.

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Part 1: The Sumerians Give Us The Unit of a Second Which Turns Out To Be A Natural Constant

While we can measure time by the completion of the Earth in its orbit around the Sun, 365.25 days, or by the rotation of the Earth once in 24 hours giving us the 24 hour day, we measure the day by a division of it into 24 equal units we call the hour because the ancient Sumerians divided the day from sunrise to sunset into 12 hours because they could measure time in the day by the Sun's position in the sky as determined by a shadow cast by it on the ground that moves through 12 divisions in a day, each division called an hour. 12 hours are then added on for the night from sunset to sunrise, so we have the 24 hour day from sunrise to sunrise, or sunset to sunset. But why choose 12 divisions which gives us the duration of the hour? I believe the reason is because 12 is the first abundant number. An abundant number means it is divisible evenly by so many integers preceding it, that their sum is greater than the number itself. That is, 12 is evenly divisible by 1,2,3,4,6 which is greater than 12:

$$1+2+3+4+6=16>12$$

There is more reason to choose 12 and that is what it is divisible by. Firstly it is divisible by the two smallest primes 2 and 3, the factors by which no integer can be reduced to further. 2 times 3 is 6 and 12 is evenly divisible by 6 and 6 is of primary importance in mathematics in that the six-sided regular polygon, the regular hexagon, has its radii equal in lengths to its sides, something, for one thing, that makes it easy as a tool for computing pi (π) the ratio of the circumference of a circle to its diameter. This because inscribed in a circle it approximates the circle, meaning its perimeter of six, if each side is taken as one, gives its diameter is two, meaning π is close to six divided by two is three. Further twelve is evenly divisible by 4, and the four-sided square is one of the regular polygons that tessellate meaning the square can tile a surface without leaving gaps. This makes it suitable for a coordinate system to specify a point in the plane or space. Such a coordinate system is the first we learn of in school, and is the most used. In fact, other coordinate systems are defined in terms of it like spherical systems where the angles are measured from a set of rectangular axes.

The other two regular polygons that tessellate are the equilateral triangle and our regular hexagon.

The Sumerians use a base 60 (sexagesimal) counting system because 60 is evenly divisible by so much as well:

1,2,3,4,5,6,10, 12, 15, 20, 30

Making it an abundant number as well, it adds up to 108, which is much greater than 60. It is important to have 5 because in the regular pentagon it determines the golden ratio, phi (ϕ), which is recurrent throughout Nature. Life more often meets up with 5-fold symmetry, like a starfish with five arms, a human with two legs, two arms, and a head, or five fingers on each hand. The physical more often meets up with six-fold symmetry, like in the points on a snowflake. We then have our base unit of one second comes from dividing our day into 24 hours and each of those hours into 60 minutes, and each of those minutes into 60 seconds. Thus the unit of a second comes to us from the ancient Sumerians, but I find the unit of a second is a natural constant for the the atom and the solar system.

So we have to ask did ancient aliens give the Sumerians their method of measuring time with the 24 hour day, and base 60 sexagesimal counting. Indeed, they were the first to settle down from hunting with stone spearpoint and following the herds to invent agriculture, architecture, mathematics, and writing and their myths say they were given this knowledge from "Those who came from the above".

This second I found is the base unit of the orbital dynamics of the solar system. I found I could create three operators, one that acts on the radius of the proton to its mass, and the other that acts on the radius of the Sun to its mass, and one that acts on angular momentum to speed. h is Planck's constant, G is the universal constant of gravitation, c is the speed of light, α is the fine structure constant, r_p is the radius of a proton, m_p is the mass of a proton, M_m is the mass of the Moon, R_m is its radius, and the EarthDay is the rotation period of the Earth:

$$1) \quad \left(\frac{1}{6\alpha^2} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi h}{Gc}} \right) \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} = 1second$$

$$2) \quad \left(\frac{M_m(EarthDay)}{R_m} \right) \cdot \frac{R_\odot}{M_\odot} = 1second$$

$$3) \quad \left(\sqrt{\frac{2}{3} \cdot \frac{\pi r_p}{\alpha^4 G m_p^3}} \right) \frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{h_p}{c} = 1second$$

They seem to suggest that the Earth orbit might be quantized in terms of the Moon and a base unit of one second.

We say there is a Planck constant for the solar system. We do it with a base unit of one second because equations 1 and 2 suggest we should. We suggest it is such that it is given by the standard Planck constant for the atom, h , times some constant, C , and the Kinetic energy of the Earth.

$$4) \quad \hbar_\odot = (hC)KE_e$$

$$5) \quad hC = 1second$$

Where

$$6). \quad C = \frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{1}{\alpha^2 c} \sqrt{\frac{2}{3} \cdot \frac{\pi r_p}{G m_p^3}}$$

Where equation 6 comes from equation 3.

We derive the value of our solar Planck constant

$$C = \frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{1}{\alpha^2 c} \sqrt{\frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{2\pi r_p}{G m_p^3}} =$$

$$\frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{18769}{299792458} \sqrt{\frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{2\pi(0.833E - 15)}{(6.67408E - 11)(1.67262E - 27)^3}}$$

$$=1.55976565E33$$

$$= \frac{s}{m} \sqrt{\frac{m}{kg^3} \cdot \frac{s^2 kg}{m^3}} = \frac{s}{m} \sqrt{\frac{s^2}{kg^2 m^2}} = \frac{s}{m} \cdot \frac{s}{kg \cdot m} = \frac{1}{kg} \cdot \frac{s^2}{m^2}$$

$$\frac{1}{C} = kg \frac{m^2}{s^2} = \frac{1}{2} m v^2 = \text{energy}$$

$$hC = (6.62607E - 34)(1.55976565E33) = 1.03351 \text{seconds} \approx 1.0 \text{seconds}$$

$$hC = \left(kg \frac{m}{s^2} \cdot m \cdot s \right) \left(\frac{1}{kg} \cdot \frac{s^2}{m^2} \right)$$

$$= \left(kg \frac{m^2}{s} \right) \left(\frac{1}{kg} \cdot \frac{s^2}{m^2} \right) = \text{seconds}$$

$$KE_{\text{earth}} = \frac{1}{2} (5.972E24 kg) (30,290 m/s)^2 = 2.7396E33 J$$

$$\hbar_{\odot} = (hC) KE_{\text{earth}} = (1.03351s)(2.7396E33 J) = 2.8314E33 J \cdot s$$

Now we show that our Planck constant for the solar system gives the base unit of one second for the quantization. We call our solar Planck constant \hbar_{\odot} and find the wavelength for the Moon which is the ground state for the solar system:

$$7) \quad \lambda_{\text{moon}} = \frac{\hbar_{\odot}^2}{GM_m^3} = \frac{(2.8314E33)^2}{(6.67408E - 11)(7.34763E22 kg)^3} = 3.0281E8 m$$

Then wavelength associated with the Moon divided by the speed of light should be 1 second if our planetary system is quantized in terms of the Moon and a base unit of one second. We have

$$8) \quad \frac{\lambda_{\text{moon}}}{c} = \frac{3.0281E8 m}{299,792,458 m/s} = 1.010 \text{seconds}$$

And we see it is, so we have

$$9) \quad \frac{\lambda_{\text{moon}}}{c} = 1 \text{second}$$

The solution for the orbit of the Earth around Sun with the Schrödinger wave equation can be inferred from the solution for an electron around a proton in the a hydrogen atom with the Schrödinger wave equation. The Schrödinger wave equation is, in spherical coordinates

10)

$$-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \left[\frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r^2 \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \right) + \frac{1}{r^2 \sin \theta} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \left(\sin \theta \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \right) + \frac{1}{r^2 \sin^2 \theta} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \phi^2} \right] \psi + V(r)\psi = E\psi$$

Its solution for the atom is

$$11) \quad E = -\frac{Z^2(k_e e^2)^2 m_e}{2\hbar^2 n^2}$$

$$12) \quad r_n = \frac{n^2 \hbar^2}{Z k_e e^2 m_e}$$

E is the energy for an electron orbiting Z protons and r_n , is the orbital shell for an electron with Z protons, n the orbital number. I find the solution for the Earth around the Sun utilizes the Moon around the Earth. This is different than with the atom because planets and moons are not all the same size and mass like electrons and protons are, and they don't jump from orbit to orbit like electrons do. I find that for the Earth around the Sun

$$13) \quad KE_e = \sqrt{n} \frac{R_\odot}{R_m} \cdot \frac{G^2 M_e^2 M_m^3}{2\hbar_\odot^2}$$

$$14) \quad r_n = \frac{2\hbar_\odot^2}{GM_m^3} \cdot \frac{R_\odot}{R_m} \cdot \frac{1}{\sqrt{n}}$$

KE_e is the kinetic energy of the Earth, and r_n is the planet's orbit. R_\odot is the radius of the Sun, r_m is the radius of the Moon's orbit, M_e is the mass of the Earth, M_m is the mass of the Moon, n is the orbit number of the Earth which is 3 and \hbar_\odot is the Planck constant for the solar system. Instead of having Z protons, we have R_\odot/R_m the radius of the Sun normalized by the radius of the Moon. It is has always been an amazing fact the the sizes of the Moon and the Sun are such that given their orbital distances, the Moon as seen from the Earth perfectly eclipses the Sun. This becomes part of the theory and we suggest it is a condition for sophisticated planets that harbor life by writing it:

$$15) \quad \frac{r_{planet}}{r_{moon}} \approx \frac{R_{star}}{R_{moon}}$$

That is the orbital radius of the planet (Earth) to the orbital radius of its moon (The Moon) is about equal to the the radius of the star (The Sun) to the radius of its moon (The Moon). We say the system is quantized by the Moon and the base unit of one second. It is a fact that the Moon orbiting the Earth optimizes the conditions for life on Earth because it holds the Earth at its inclination to its orbit around the Sun allowing for the seasons, preventing extreme hot and extreme cold. Let us now see if our solar Planck constant works...

$$16) \quad \frac{R_\odot}{R_m} = \frac{6.96E8m}{1737400m} = 400.5986$$

$$KE_e = (1.732)(400.5986) \frac{(6.67408E-11)^2 (5.972E24kg)^2 (7.347673E22kg)^3}{2(2.8314E33)^2} =$$

$$= 2.727E36J$$

The kinetic energy of the Earth is

$$KE_e = \frac{1}{2} (5.972E24kg) (30,290m/s)^2 = 2.7396E33J$$

The accuracy of our equation is:

$$\frac{2.727E36J}{2.7396E33J} 100 = 99.5 \%$$

Which is very good. Thus we have solved the Earth/Moon/Sun System with our spacetime operators by using them to find a Planck constant for the solar system.

We want to suggest that the base 60 dynamic applied to the rotational velocity of the Earth to measure time has a natural property associated with the atom and the Earth/Moon/Sun orbital system as a solution to the atom's wave equation. The Earth day is given by, in seconds

$$\left(\frac{1day}{24hrs} \right) \left(\frac{1hr}{60min} \right) \left(\frac{1min}{60sec} \right) = \frac{1}{86400} \frac{day}{sec}$$

This gives since $2 \cdot 3 \cdot 4 = 24$

$$2 \cdot 3 \cdot 4 \cdot 60 \cdot 60 = 86400seconds/day$$

Thus we have as factors for the seconds per day the smallest primes 2 and 3, and the 4 of rectangular coordinate systems, and the versatile, abundant, 60. We then suggest the second is dynamic in terms of what the ancients gave us because 86400 seconds comes from $2 \cdot 3 \cdot 4 \cdot 60 \cdot 60$ and this I suggest is connected to Nature because the Earth rotates at a speed that gives from these ancient factors the duration of a second that I found is the base unit of the atomic systems and our planetary system, in particular of our Earth/Moon/Sun system as a solution of the Schrödinger wave equation that solves the same atomic system, which I will go into right now.

We see the spacetime operators solve the atom by giving us the radius of a proton. We set equation 3 equal to equation 1

$$3) \left(\sqrt{\frac{2}{3} \cdot \frac{\pi r_p}{\alpha^4 G m_p^3}} \right) \frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{h}{c} = 1second$$

$$1). \left(\frac{1}{6\alpha^2} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi h}{Gc}} \right) \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} = 1second$$

These two yield

$$17). \quad r_p = \frac{2}{3} \cdot \frac{h}{cm_p}$$

I find this is close to the experimental value of the radius of a proton. I find I can arrive at this radius of a proton another way, energy is given by Planck's constant and frequency

$$E = hf$$

We have

$$f = 1/s, h = J \cdot s, hf = (J \cdot s)(1/s) = J$$

$$E = J = \text{Joules} = \text{energy}$$

We take the rest energy of the mass of a proton m_p :

$$E = m_p c^2$$

The frequency of a proton is

$$f_p = \frac{m_p c^2}{h}$$

Since our theory gave us the factor of $2/3$ for the radius of a proton we have:

$$\frac{m_p c^2}{h} \cdot \frac{r_p}{c} = \frac{2}{3} \approx \phi = \frac{m_p c}{h} r_p$$

$$m_p r_p = \frac{2}{3} \cdot \frac{h}{c}$$

The radius of a proton is then

$$r_p = \frac{2}{3} \cdot \frac{h}{cm_p}$$

This is close to the CODATA value for the proton radius around 2018 ($0.842E-15m$). The result is

$$r_p = \frac{2}{3} \cdot \frac{6.62607E-34}{(299,792,458)(1.67262E-27)} = 0.88094E-15m$$

We find it may be that the radius of a proton is actually

$$18) \quad r_p = \phi \cdot \frac{h}{cm_p} = 0.816632E-15m$$

Where ϕ is the golden ratio constant (0.618...). This is more along the lines of more recent measurements. Both equations 17 and 18 for the radius of the proton can be right depending on the dynamics of what is going on; the radius of a proton is not precisely defined, it is more of a fuzzy cloud of subatomic particles. Thus we have solved the atom with our spacetime operators by producing the radius of a proton.

Indeed if the dynamics of the factors the ancients gave us to create the duration of a second are connected to the dynamics of stars systems then then the second should define the rotational angular momentum of the Earth since we divide the rotation period of the Earth into these factors to get the unit of second, and should be connected to our Planck constant for the solar system which is in units of angular momentum as well, as is Planck's constant for the atom.

The angular momentum of the Earth with respect to the Sun is $2.66E40$ kg m²/s. The rotational angular momentum is $7.05E33$ kg m²/s. In orbit angular momentum is given by

$$L = 2\pi Mfr^2$$

For a uniform rotational sphere it is given by

$$L = \frac{4}{5}\pi Mfr^2$$

We found our solar system Planck constant was

$$\hbar_{\odot} = 2.8314E33J \cdot s$$

This gives

$$19) \quad \frac{L_{earth}}{\hbar_{\odot}} = \frac{7.05E33}{2.8314E33} = 2.4899 \approx 2.5 = 2\frac{1}{2}$$

We are now equipped to show that the ancient Sumerians were right in dividing the rotation period of the Earth (the day) into 24 units (the hour) because

$$2.5(24) = 60$$

That is

$$20). \quad \frac{L_{earth}}{\hbar_{\odot}} 24 = 60$$

Which is to say the angular momentum of the Earth to its Planck constant gives the base 60 counting in terms of the 24 hour day, the 60 of 60 minutes in an hour, and 60 seconds in a minute, that determine our base unit of duration we call a second that happens to be, as I have shown, the base unit of the wave solution to the atom and the Earth/Moon/Sun system.

Our equation in this paper for the Earth energy as a solution of the wave equation (eq. 13)

$$13). \quad KE_e = \sqrt{n} \frac{R_{\odot}}{R_m} \cdot \frac{G^2 M_e^2 M_m^3}{2\hbar_{\odot}^2}$$

does not depend on the Moon's distance from the Earth, only its mass. The Moon slows the Earth rotation and this in turn expands the Moon's orbit, so it is getting larger, the Earth loses energy to the Moon. The Earth day gets longer by 0.0067 hours per million years, and the Moon's orbit gets 3.78 cm larger per year. Equation 20

$$20) \frac{L_{earth}}{\hbar_{\odot}} 24 = 60$$

only specifies divide the day into 24 units, and hours into 60 minutes and minutes into 60 seconds, regardless of what the Earth rotational velocity is. But it was more or less the same as it is now when the Sumerians started civilization. But it may be that it holds for when the Earth day is such that when the Moon perfectly eclipses the Sun, which we said might be a condition for the optimization of life preventing extreme hot and cold. That is when 15 holds

$$15) \frac{r_{planet}}{r_{moon}} \approx \frac{R_{star}}{R_{moon}}$$

Which holds for today and held for the ancient Sumerians and holds for when the Earth rotation gives the duration of a second we have today.

We want the basis set of equations for the solar system. We have

$$\lambda_{moon} = \frac{\hbar_{\odot}^2}{GM_m^3} = 3.0281E8m$$

We have from equation

$$\frac{\lambda_{moon}}{c} = \frac{\hbar_{\odot}^2}{GM_m^3} \cdot \frac{1}{c} = 1.0seconds$$

We have equations

$$\hbar_{\odot} = (hC)KE_e$$

$$hC = 1second$$

We have equations

$$\left(\sqrt{\frac{2}{3} \cdot \frac{\pi r_p}{\alpha^4 G m_p^3}} \right) \frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{h}{c} = 1second$$

$$\left(\frac{1}{6\alpha^2} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi h}{Gc}} \right) \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} = 1second$$

$$1second = \frac{KE_m}{KE_e}(EarthDay)$$

From these it becomes clear that

$$21) \quad \hbar_{\odot} = \frac{GM_m^3 c}{KE_e}$$

$$22) \quad KE_e = \frac{GM_m^3 c}{\hbar_{\odot}}$$

$$23) \quad \hbar_{\odot} = \left(\frac{1}{6\alpha^2} \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi\hbar}{Gc}} \right) KE_e$$

Thus combining equation 20 with the following...

$$\frac{\lambda_{moon}}{c} = 1second$$

$$hC = 1second$$

$$\hbar_{\odot} = (hC)KE_e$$

$$21). \quad KE_e = \frac{GM_m^3 c}{\hbar_{\odot}}$$

$$20). \quad \frac{L_{earth}}{\hbar_{\odot}} 24 = 60$$

Which gives

$$\begin{aligned} 24) \quad 1second &= \left(\frac{24}{60} \right)^2 \frac{L_{earth}^2}{GM_m^3 c} \\ &= \left(\frac{24}{60} \right)^2 \frac{(7.05E33)^2}{(6.67408E-11)((7.347673E22kg)^3(299792458m/s)} = \\ &\left(\frac{24}{60} \right)^2 6.262sec = 1.002seconds = 1.00seconds \end{aligned}$$

This is very accurate to give us a second. But notice 6.262 is approximately 2π . We see that

$$25) \quad 1 = \left(\frac{24}{60} \right)^2 2\pi$$

2π is the circumference of a unit circle, it could be that the circumference of the Earth orbit, can be taken as 1 (unity) and essentially we have the mystery of base 60 and the 24 hour day of the ancient Sumerians is solved, it connects unit circle to 1 (unity).

$$26). \quad \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} = \frac{24}{60} \sqrt{\pi}$$

$$27) \quad \cos(45^\circ) = \cos(\pi/4) = \frac{24}{60} \sqrt{\pi}$$

I came up with a physical theory for certain aspects of reality that showed that our solar system had a wave equation solution, where the wave equation was developed for describing atomic systems, among other things, and is at the heart of quantum physics, the modern physics that describes things on the micro-scale and our planetary system is on the macro-scale. I found it was based on the Moon that orbits the Earth, which seems to be some kind of a natural yardstick, and was further based on the unit of a second for measuring time as the base unit, which I found turns out to be some kind of a natural constant. This natural constant of a second also, in the theory, predicts the radius of a proton, the fundamental unit of the atom, and as such a gap is bridged between the microcosmos and the macrocosmos. Further it resulted in a description of the hydrocarbons, which are the backbones of the chemistry of life. Bringing in the biological like this makes it the rudiments of a theory of everything,

The interesting thing is, though, that the second was not designed, originally, as a natural constant, but came to us ultimately from the ancient Sumerians of Mesopotamia, who were some of the first to settle down from hunting with stone spearpoints to invent agriculture, mathematics, writing, metallurgy, architecture... to invent civilization.

The idea was to divide the day into twelve hours, and measure each hour by the position of the Sun in the sky, as measured by the shadow cast by a rod onto a plate with lines to measure the time of day. They chose twelve hours in a day because 12 is the smallest abundant number, which is to say it is evenly divisible by 1,2,3,4,6 whose sum is 16 which is greater than twelve.

Their counting system was base 60 (sexagesimal) which means they started counting again after counting to 60 where our system is base 10 (decimal) which means we start counting again after 10. They chose base 60 because sixty, aside from being an abundant number — its divisors add up to a value greater than it — it is the first number divisible by the first 6 counting numbers, 1,2,3,4,5,6 aside from being evenly divisible by 10,12,15,30.

This led to the ancient Babylonians dividing the hour into 60 minutes, and the minute into 60 seconds. This in the end led to the ancient Greeks using it for astronomy, and the Italians to in the Middle Ages build the first clocks with hours, minutes, and seconds. In the end they gave us our clocks and the way we measure time in the West, today. The ancient Egyptians, separately and independently invented civilization from the Sumerians, but were never invaded by tribes, like in Sumer, who stayed and adopted their math and writing, but rather were isolated by desert, ocean, and forests, so as not to spread their invention of Mathematics, writing, and architecture to the rest of the world, at least until they and the ancient Greeks interacted and shared knowledges in several exchanges where ancient Greek scholars wandered into Egypt. But, the ancient Egyptians also divided the day into 12 hours and invented sun dials to tell time as such. However, we got the 12 hour day, or 24 hour day from sunrise to sunrise and sunset to sunset, from the ancient Sumerians.

However, myself, having been born in the West I was more aware of Sumer and Egypt, than India, and indeed while Sumer and Egypt started civilizations, so did the people who brought it to India, to the Dravidians, and the idea of transmigration of the soul who were from its outskirts, who brought it from the Indus Valley where the rivers were, they were the Indus Valley

Civilization, just as old as Sumer and Egypt. It would seem civilizations always started along rivers, the Tigris and Euphrates in Mesopotamia, and the Nile in Egypt.

However, after having looked at my theory for reality in terms of the base 60 of Sumer that gave us the second, and how its dynamics could have coincided with modern physics, and suggesting that it was given to them by ancient Aliens, because they said they got their knowledge from those who came from the heavens, the Anunaki, I began to look at the system that ancient India used to measure time, and I found that they used base 60 as well, but in a very reversed way from what we got from Mesopotamia, the Babylonians, and ancient Greeks. And, I found further, that their system of base 60 describes certain aspects of Nature as well.

Before the colonization of India by the British, another system of measuring time from ancient times was used, and it was called the Bharat Clock. There are efforts in India today to return to this, and they suggest for contemporary physics it serves better, as well as it is more efficient for productivity in the work force. Further still they explain that it is based on Natural phenomenon in the Universe, and that in the method of the West, it is not. I would take issue with that not just because my theory for reality shows the Mesopotamian system gives us the unit of a second in planetary systems, atomic systems, and biological systems, which they could not know about, but because it does have an elegance that works well for the the periods of celestial motions, and has since its inception, though I can see advantages in their system as well.

The Hindu system is quite inverted from ours, but my theory of physical reality shows the two systems are profoundly connected in a way that can be quite revealing. We measure the year as 365.25 days which is close to the 360 degrees in a circle. As such the Earth moves around the Sun in its orbit through neatly about 1 degree per day. The Sumerians gave us the 360 degrees circle, because in their base 60 counting 6 times 60 is 360, and 6 is the most dynamic number, a six-sided regular polygon has its radii equal to its sides, which mathematically has many advantages for solving problems. It occurs in Nature as the closest packing of equal radius spheres, the so so called six around one, typical in Nature of petal arrangements around a center in a flower, and 6-fold symmetry is typical of the physical, like snowflakes forming six-points as ice crystals fall through cold air. 5-fold symmetry is typical of life, like two eyes and nose and a mouth, or two arms, two legs, and a head.

The Earth then rotates close to 360 times in a year, close to the time for it to complete an orbit around the Sun. Each rotation is a day, and from the Sumerians we divided that day into 24 hours. 60 divided by 24 is 2.5 and as it would turn out 2.5 is the factor than connects the Hindu system to the Western system. As we shall see, my theory finds this factor is a pivotal factor of Nature. Let's look at our system and theirs. We have

$(365.25 \text{ days})(24 \text{ hours})(60 \text{ minutes})(60 \text{ seconds})=31557600 \text{ seconds/year}$

And the seconds in a day are

$(24 \text{ hours})(60 \text{ minutes})(60 \text{ seconds})=86400 \text{ seconds/day}$

Thus we divide the hour into 60 minutes, and the minutes into 60 seconds. The Hindu Vedic System has a day is 60 ghatika of 24 minutes each, each ghatika is divided into 60 palas of 24 seconds each, and each pala is divided into 60 vispalas, each vispala of 0.4 seconds each. So where our system has a base unit of 1 second, theirs has a base unit of 0.4 seconds, so that could be an advantage to their system, a smaller unit of time is more refined. Further their day is divided into 60 units, ours into only 24, so their hour, the ghatika is only 24 minutes long, and ours is 60 minutes long, The proponents in India say since when working and doing chores we

do a few chores in an hour, they do about one per ghatika is 24 minutes, which makes the measure of time more manageable. That could be an advantage I think. They say our hour is so long because the lines had to be far apart on the Egyptian Sun Dial so the shadow cast by the Sun didn't cross-over onto another line. But today, with modern technology we can make clock lines marking hours closer together and measure them with a pointer hand pointing to them without any problems, and the result is we would have a smaller more refined hour (60 of them in a day as opposed to 24). They suggest this method of measuring time would work better in science and engineering as well, that we have to get away from the way sun dials had to be made in Egypt in ancient times.

But they further point out that their system describes Nature. They say theirs are 108,000 vispalas in a day, and 108,000 vispalas in a night giving 216,000 vispalas in a 24 hour day. The diameter of the Sun is 108 that of the Earth, and the average distance from the Sun to the Earth is 108 solar diameters, and the average distance from the Moon to Earth is 108 lunar diameters. $108(10)(10)(10)=108,000$. Ourselves and them use base 10 counting, and that is probably because we have ten fingers to count on.

Conclusion

In conclusion we have that the unit of a second as derived from the Mesopotamians is a Natural constant. As well we see the Hindu Vedic system describes Nature as well. It says

$$2R_{\odot} = 2(6.957E8m) = 1.3914E9meters \quad (R_{\odot} = SolarRadius)$$

$$r_e = 1.496E11m \quad (r_e = EarthOrbit)$$

$$\frac{r_e}{2R_{\odot}} = 107.52 \approx 108$$

$$2R_{moon} = 2(1.74E6m) = 3.48E6m \quad (R_{moon} = LunarRadius)$$

$$r_{moon} = 3.845E8m \quad (r_{moon} = LunarOrbit)$$

$$\frac{r_m}{2R_{moon}} = 110 \approx 108$$

$$\frac{(86,000sec/day)}{2} = \frac{43200}{0.4sec/vispala} = 108,000vispalas/day$$

$$108(10)(10)(10) = 108,000$$

To see how this is connected to nature we would have to go into the significance of base 10 counting as we did with base 60 counting. But interesting here is that

$$\frac{r_e}{2R_{\odot}} = 107.52 \approx 108$$

$$\frac{r_m}{2R_{moon}} = 110 \approx 108$$

$$\frac{R_{\odot}}{R_e} = \frac{6.957E8m}{6,371,000m} = 109 \approx 108$$

because

$$13. KE_e = \sqrt{n} \frac{R_{\odot}}{R_m} \cdot \frac{G^2 M_e^2 M_m^3}{2\hbar_{\odot}^2}$$

where

$$15. \frac{r_{planet}}{r_{moon}} \approx \frac{R_{star}}{R_{moon}}$$

$$16. \frac{R_{\odot}}{R_m} = \frac{6.96E8m}{1737400m} = 400.5986$$

Which is to say radius of the Sun to the radius of the Moon in the planetary equation plays the role of the number of protons (Z) in an element for the energy of the electron orbits in the atomic equation and that the Moon perfectly eclipses the Sun as see from the earth (eq 15) might be a condition for sophisticated habitable star systems, we know the Moon allows for the seasons making life very successful on Earth by preventing temperature extremes. So in the Hindu Vedic system the diameters of the Sun and Moon fitting into Earth orbit and Lunar orbit the same amount might play a similar role in a theory. You would have to go into base 10 like we did with base 60. We have

West

24 hours

60 minutes

60 seconds

India

60 hours

24 minutes

24 seconds

A sort of inversion of things. The incredible thing here is that the wonderful equations, equations 19 and 20:

$$19. \frac{L_{earth}}{\hbar_{\odot}} = \frac{7.05E33}{2.8314E33} = 2.4899 \approx 2.5 = 2\frac{1}{2}$$

$$20. \frac{L_{earth}}{\hbar_{\odot}} 24 = 60$$

unify the Mesopotamian system with the Hindu system because

$$1 \text{ vispala} = 0.4 \text{ seconds}$$

$$(0.4s)(2.5) = 1 \text{ second}$$

This suggests that the Hindu system is just as Natural as the Western system.

Equation 25 that says

$$25) \quad 1 = \left(\frac{24}{60}\right)^2 2\pi$$

$$1 \text{ hour} = (60 \text{ min/hour})(60 \text{ sec/min}) = 3600 \text{ sec} = 1 \text{ Western Hour}$$

$$1 \text{ vispala} = 0.4 \text{ sec}$$

$$60 \text{ vispala} = (60)(0.4 \text{ sec}) = 24 \text{ sec} = 1 \text{ pala}$$

$$60 \text{ pala} = (60)(24 \text{ sec}) = 1440 \text{ sec} = 24 \text{ min} = 1 \text{ ghaticka} = 1 \text{ Hindu Hour}$$

$$1 = \frac{(1440 \text{ sec})^2}{(3600 \text{ sec})^2} 2\pi$$

$$1 = \frac{(1 \text{ ghaticka})^2}{(1 \text{ hour})^2} 2\pi$$

$$28). \quad 1 = \frac{\text{Hindu Hour}^2}{\text{Western Hour}^2} 2\pi$$

$$1 = \frac{(60 \text{ pala})^2}{(60 \text{ min})^2} 2\pi = \frac{(24 \text{ min})^2}{(60 \text{ min})^2} 2\pi$$

$$1 = \frac{((60)(24 \text{ sec}))^2}{((60)(60 \text{ sec}))^2} 2\pi = \frac{(60 \text{ pala})^2}{(60 \text{ sec})^2} 2\pi = \frac{(24 \text{ sec})^2}{(60 \text{ sec})^2} 2\pi$$

where 2π is the circumference of a unit circle, and we have unity on the left, so it could be if you combine the Indian system of measuring time with the Western system you would have a system of units for the solar system where the equations work out nicely.

Part 2: Biological Life Part of a Universal Natural Process In The Universe

Introduction I have a theory for the star systems, the planets and their suns, wherein such systems are solved with the Schrödinger wave equation that is used to solve atomic systems. The result is that star systems and atomic systems, systems on the macro scales and micro scales, are governed by the same underlying principles. It came to pass that this theory indicated an overlap with biological systems indicating that biological life could be part of the same idea, and that is what I hope to pull out of that paper and develop here.

The theory for the planets, which also predicted the radius of a proton, which is one of the fundamental particles out of which matter is made, suggested that star systems which support life are a part of a Universal natural process. One of the conditions for star systems that support life made use of the interesting fact that has mystified science for some time now, that the Moon is the right size and distance from the Earth that it nearly perfectly eclipses the Sun. The reason a moon would be necessary for life to be optimally successful on a habitable planet is that we know our moon that orbits our Earth, makes life here successful because it holds the Earth at its inclination to its orbit around the Sun allowing for the seasons, thus preventing extreme hot and extreme cold.

Interestingly, the solution for the planets of the Schrödinger wave equation, was quantized in terms of the Earth's moon, and a base unit of one second. The Moon seems to be some sort of a natural yardstick. The strange thing is that the basis unit of time is one second and the second was not developed with the planets and atoms in mind, so it is strange that it lands upon the function of a natural constant in our theory. In the theory (*An Abstract Theory of Reality*, *Beardsley 2024*) I talk a little about why that might be. The second came to us from the Ancient Sumerians, who invented civilization with settling down from following the herds and hunting with stone spearpoint to invent agriculture, metallurgy, writing, and mathematics. They had a base 60 counting system, and found it convenient then to divide the Earth day (rotation period) into 24 hours, which in the end became adopted by the world. Their base 60 counting resulted in the Babylonians dividing the hour into 60 minutes, and that in turn into 60 seconds, and that is how we have the duration of a second we have today. They chose base 60 (sexagesimal) because 60 is evenly divisible by so much from which they gave us the 12 hour day and 12 hour night or 24 hour day from sunrise to sunrise, sunset to sunset. 12 times 5 is 60, also 60 times 6 is 360, they gave us the 360 degree circle as well.

In this paper I show that the same unit of a second that describes planetary systems and atomic system in common describes hydrocarbons, the skeletons of biological life chemistry. I further show that it predicts the atomic radii of the hydrogen and carbon atoms from which such skeletons are made. Hydrogen and carbon are the most abundant elements in life chemistry, carbon is the core element upon which life is made, and hydrogen is the simplest element, element one in the periodic table of the elements, consisting of 1 proton, and is the most abundant element in the universe by far, and plays the dominant role in all of chemistry.

A Theory For Biological Hydrocarbons I have found that the basis unit of one second is not just a Natural constant for physical systems like the atom and the planets around the Sun (See my paper *An Abstract Theory of Reality, Beardsley 2024*) but for the basis of biological life, that it is in the sixfold Nature of the chemical skeletons from which life is built, the hydrocarbons. I found

$$1). \quad 1second = \frac{1}{6\alpha^2} \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi h}{Gc}}$$

$$2). \quad 1second = \frac{KE_m}{KE_e}(EarthDay)$$

Where $\alpha = 1/137$ is the fine structure constant, r_p is the radius of a proton, m_p is the mass of a proton, h is Planck's constant, G is the constant of gravitation, c is the speed of light, KE_m is the kinetic energy of the Moon, KE_e is the kinetic energy of the Earth, and *EarthDay* is the rotation period of the Earth is one day.

The first can be written:

$$3). \quad \frac{1}{\alpha^2 m_p} \sqrt{\frac{h 4\pi r_p^2}{Gc}} = 6proton \cdot seconds = carbon(C)$$

$$4). \quad \frac{1}{\alpha^2 m_p} \sqrt{\frac{h 4\pi r_p^2}{Gc}} = 1proton \cdot 6seconds = hydrogen(H)$$

From which instead of saying the left sides of these equations are seconds, we say they are proton-seconds by not letting the units of m_p cancel with the bodies of these equations on the left, which are in units of mass, but rather divide into them, giving us a number of protons. I say this is the biological because these are the hydrocarbons the backbones of biological chemistry. We see they display sixfold symmetry. I can generate integer numbers of protons from the time values from these equations for all of the elements with a computer program. Some results are:

```
By what value would you like to increment?: 0.25
How many values would you like to calculate for t in equation? (No more than 100): 100
24.1199 protons 0.250000 second 0.119904 decpart
12.0600 protons 0.500000 second 0.059952 decpart
8.0400 protons 0.750000 second 0.039968 decpart
6.0300 protons 1.000000 second 0.029976 decpart
4.0200 protons 1.500000 second 0.019984 decpart
3.0150 protons 2.000000 second 0.014988 decpart
2.1927 protons 2.750000 second 0.192718 decpart
2.0100 protons 3.000000 second 0.009992 decpart
1.2060 protons 5.000000 second 0.205995 decpart
1.1486 protons 5.250000 second 0.148567 decpart
1.0964 protons 5.500000 second 0.096359 decpart
1.0487 protons 5.750000 second 0.048691 decpart
1.0050 protons 6.000000 second 0.004996 decpart
0.2487 protons 24.250000 second 0.248659 decpart
0.2461 protons 24.500000 second 0.246121 decpart
0.2436 protons 24.750000 second 0.243635 decpart
Program ended with exit code: 0
```

A very interesting thing here is looking at the values generated by the program, the smallest integer value 1 second produces 6 protons (carbon) and the largest integer value 6 seconds produces one proton (hydrogen). Beyond six seconds you have fractional protons, and the rest of the elements heavier than carbon are formed by fractional seconds. These are the hydrocarbons the backbones of biological chemistry. And carbon is the core element of life. We see the duration of the base unit of measuring time, 1 second, given to us by the ancients (the base 60, sexagesimal, system of counting of the Sumerians who invented math and writing and started civilization), is perfect for the mathematical formulation of life chemistry. Here is the code for the program, it finds integer solutions for time values, incremented by the program at the discretion of the user:

```
#include <stdio.h>
#include <math.h>
int main(int argc, const char * argv[]) {

    int n;
    float value=0, increment,t=0, p=1.67262E-27, h=6.62607E-34,G=6.67408E-11,
    c=299792458,protons[100],r=0.833E-15;

    do
    {
        printf("By what value would you like to increment?: ");
        scanf("%f", &increment);
        printf("How many values would you like to calculate for t in equation 1 (no more than 100?): ");
        scanf("%i", &n);
    }
    while (n>=101);
    {

        for (int i=0; i<n;i++)
        {
            protons[i]=((137*137)/(t*p))*sqrt(h*4*(3.14159)*(r*r)/(G*c));

            int intpart=(int)protons[i];
            float decpart=protons[i]-intpart;
            t=t+increment;
            if (decpart<0.25)
            { printf("%.4f protons %f seconds %f decpart \n", protons[i], t-increment, decpart);
              }
            }
        }
    }
```

We have that

$$\frac{1}{\alpha^2} \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi\hbar}{Gc}} = 18769 \frac{0.833E-15}{1.67262E-27} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi(6.62607E-34)}{(6.67408E-11)(299,792458)}} = 6.029978s \approx 6s$$

Since this 6 seconds is also proton-seconds we have

$$5). \quad \frac{1}{6_{protons}} \cdot \frac{1}{\alpha^2} \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi\hbar}{Gc}} = 1second \text{ is carbon (C)}$$

$$6). \quad \frac{1}{1_{proton}} \cdot \frac{1}{\alpha^2} \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi\hbar}{Gc}} = 6seconds \text{ is hydrogen (H)}$$

Our Theory For Hydrocarbons With all that has been said we are equipped to proceed. We want to consider the radius of a hydrogen atom and the radius of a carbon atom. The radius of a carbon atom given in your periodic table of the elements is often 70 to 76 picometers. The covalent radius of hydrogen is given as 31 picometers. The atomic radius of hydrogen is 53 picometers and the atomic radius of carbon is 67 picometers. We want to consider the atomic radii of both, because the covalent radius, determined by x-ray diffraction for diatomic hydrogen, is the size of two hydrogen atoms joined H₂ divided by two, where it is measured that way, joined, in the laboratory. Carbon is C₂ divided by 2. We are interested in the single carbon and hydrogen atoms, because we want to know what our theory for their six-fold symmetry with one another in their representations in proton-seconds says about the way they combine as the skeletons of life chemistry. We start with the Planck constant, h , which is like flux, a mass (perhaps a number of particles) per second over an area. That is it is kilograms per second over square area:

$$h = 6.62607E - 34 J \cdot s = 6.62607E - 37 \frac{kg}{s} \cdot m^2$$

We have equations 1 and 2:

$$1). \quad \frac{1}{6 \text{ protons}} \cdot \frac{1}{\alpha^2} \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi h}{Gc}} = 1 \text{ second is carbon (C)}$$

$$2). \quad \frac{1}{1 \text{ proton}} \cdot \frac{1}{\alpha^2} \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi h}{Gc}} = 6 \text{ seconds is hydrogen (H)}$$

We can write these

$$\left(6.62607E - 37 \frac{kg}{s} \cdot m^2 \right) \frac{6 \text{ seconds}}{m_p} =$$

$$3). \quad \left(6.62607E - 37 \frac{kg}{s} \cdot m^2 \right) \frac{6 \text{ seconds}}{1.67262E - 27 kg} = 2.37689E - 6 m^2$$

$$\left(6.62607E - 37 \frac{kg}{s} \cdot m^2 \right) \frac{1 \text{ second}}{6 m_p} =$$

$$4). \quad \left(6.62607E - 37 \frac{kg}{s} \cdot m^2 \right) \frac{1 \text{ second}}{6(1.67262E - 27 kg)} = 6.602486E - 8 m^2$$

We have from 3 and 4...

$$5). \quad \frac{\frac{h}{m_p} \cdot \frac{(6 \text{ seconds})}{1}}{\frac{h}{m_p} \cdot \frac{(1 \text{ second})}{6}} = \frac{2.37689E - 6 m^2}{6.602486E - 8 m^2} = 35.9999 \approx 40$$

We find the ratio between the surface areas of the hydrogen and carbon atoms:

$$6). \quad H_{surface} = 4\pi(r_H^2) = 3.52989E - 20m^2$$

$$7). \quad C_{surface} = 4\pi(r_C^2) = 5.64104E - 20m^2$$

$$\frac{4\pi(53pm)^2}{4\pi(67pm)^2} = 0.62575 \approx 0.618... = \phi$$

It is the golden mean. These atomic radii are the radii between the nucleus of the atoms and their valence shell, which is what we want because the valence shell is the outermost electrons responsible for the way the hydrogen and the carbon combine to make hydrocarbons. We will write this

$$8). \quad \frac{r_H^2}{r_C^2} = \phi_{HC}$$

I am guessing the reason we have the golden mean here is that it is the number used for closest packing. But what we really want to do is look at the concept of action, for hydrogen given by six seconds and carbon given by 1 second. We take equations 1 and 2:

$$1). \quad \frac{1}{6protons} \cdot \frac{1}{\alpha^2} \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi h}{Gc}} = 1second \text{ is carbon (C)}$$

$$2). \quad \frac{1}{1proton} \cdot \frac{1}{\alpha^2} \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi h}{Gc}} = 6seconds \text{ is hydrogen (H)}$$

And, we write

$$9). \quad m_p \sqrt{\frac{Gc}{h}} \int_0^t dt = r_A$$

Where r_A is the radius of the atom, and t its time values given here by equations 1 and 2. We have for hydrogen

$$10). \quad m_p \sqrt{\frac{Gc}{h}} \int_0^t dt = (1.67262E - 27kg) \sqrt{\frac{(6.67408E - 11)(299,792,458)}{6.62607E - 34}} \int_0^{6sec} dt$$

$$=(9.2E - 12m/s)(6seconds) = 5.5E - 11m$$

This is actually very close to the radius of a hydrogen which can vary around this depending on how you are looking at it, which we said is given by 5.3E-11m. For carbon we have:

$$11). \quad m_p \sqrt{\frac{Gc}{h}} \int_0^t dt = (1.67262E - 27kg) \sqrt{\frac{(6.67408E - 11)(299,792,458)}{6.62607E - 34}} \int_0^{6sec+1sec} dt$$

$$=(9.2E - 12m/s)(7seconds) = 6.44E - 11m$$

And this is actually very close to the radius of a carbon atom which is 6.7E-11m. The thing is if we consider the bond length of the simplest hydrocarbon CH₄, methane, which can be thought of as

$$16). \quad r_H + r_C = 5.3E - 11m + 6.7E - 11m = 1.2E - 10m$$

our, equations give

$$17). \quad r_H + r_C = 5.5E - 11m + 6.44E - 11m = 1.2E - 10m$$

which are the same thing. Thus we have the basis for a theory of everything in that it includes the macro scale, the Earth/Moon/Sun System, because we had:

$$1second = \frac{KE_m}{KE_e}(EarthDay)$$

and it includes the radius of the proton which is the radius and mass of a proton and gives 1 second

$$1second = \frac{1}{6\alpha^2} \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi h}{Gc}}$$

and we have the hydrocarbons the skeleton of the chemistry of life give one second

$$1). \quad \frac{1}{6protons} \cdot \frac{1}{\alpha^2} \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi h}{Gc}} = 1second \text{ is carbon (C)}$$

$$2). \quad \frac{1}{1proton} \cdot \frac{1}{\alpha^2} \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi h}{Gc}} = 6seconds \text{ is hydrogen (H)}$$

and because they predict the radii of the carbon and hydrogen atoms at the core of life

$$10). \quad m_p \sqrt{\frac{Gc}{h}} \int_0^t dt = (1.67262E - 27kg) \sqrt{\frac{(6.67408E - 11)(299,792,458)}{6.62607E - 34}} \int_0^{6sec} dt$$

$$=(9.2E - 12m/s)(6seconds) = 5.5E - 11m$$

$$11). \quad m_p \sqrt{\frac{Gc}{h}} \int_0^t dt = (1.67262E - 27kg) \sqrt{\frac{(6.67408E - 11)(299,792,458)}{6.62607E - 34}} \int_0^{6sec+1sec} dt$$

$$=(9.2E - 12m/s)(7seconds) = 6.44E - 11m$$

We want to proceed with the elements nitrogen (N) and oxygen (O). We just did carbon and hydrogen, but hydrocarbons are then combined with primarily nitrogen and oxygen to make amino acids, the building blocks of life. DNA synthesizes them into proteins, for hair, muscles tissue, skin, nails, etc... The most basic organic compound, HNCO (isocyanic acid) is just one each of these elements. It bonds

It was shown by the Miller-Urey experiment that if a primordial Earth was mainly ammonia (NH₃), Methane (CH₄), water (H₂O) these combined under energy form 11 of the 20 biological amino acids life needs for DNA to synthesize proteins. Thus we start with nitrogen and notice the first eight element are atomic number 1 is hydrogen, atomic number 2 is helium, atomic number 3 is lithium, atomic number 4 is beryllium, atomic number 5 is boron, atomic number six is carbon, atomic number 7 is nitrogen, atomic number 8 is oxygen. The atomic numbers correspond to the the number of protons in each element.

1.	2.	3.	4.	5.	6.	7.	8.
H	He	Li	Be	B	C	N	O

We suggest the periodic table of the elements has its function in sixfold symmetry because it has 18 groups in that 6 times 3 is 18 and 3 this the first odd prime number other than one, where all prime numbers are odd except 2, and 1 defines a prime number in that a prime number is a number that is evenly divisible by itself and 1. The periodic table is then centered around hydrogen and carbon, hydrogen with one proton, carbon with six where hydrogen is given by 6 seconds and carbon is given by 1 second, all values beyond 6 seconds are fractional protons and 1 second is the smallest integer number of seconds that gives whole protons. That is, equations 1 and 2 are

$$1). \quad \frac{1}{6\text{protons}} \cdot \frac{1}{\alpha^2} \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi h}{Gc}} = 1\text{second is carbon (C)}$$

$$2). \quad \frac{1}{1\text{proton}} \cdot \frac{1}{\alpha^2} \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi h}{Gc}} = 6\text{seconds is hydrogen (H)}$$

We already had that hydrogen, the base element with 1 proton gives itself, hydrogen, and carbon with 6 protons is given by itself and hydrogen in equations 10 and 11:

$$10). \quad m_p \sqrt{\frac{Gc}{h}} \int_0^t dt = (1.67262E - 27kg) \sqrt{\frac{(6.67408E - 11)(299,792,458)}{6.62607E - 34}} \int_0^{6\text{sec}} dt$$

$$=(9.2E - 12m/s)(6\text{seconds}) = 5.5E - 11m$$

$$11). \quad m_p \sqrt{\frac{Gc}{h}} \int_0^t dt = (1.67262E - 27kg) \sqrt{\frac{(6.67408E - 11)(299,792,458)}{6.62607E - 34}} \int_0^{6\text{sec}+1\text{sec}} dt$$

$$=(9.2E - 12m/s)(7\text{seconds}) = 6.44E - 11m$$

We had that experimentally for the hydrocarbon backbones of life

$$16). \quad r_H + r_C = 5.3E - 11m + 6.7E - 11m = 1.2E - 10m$$

And, according to our theory that

$$17). \quad r_H + r_C = 5.5E - 11m + 6.44E - 11m = 1.2E - 10m$$

We want to consider that elements 6, 7, 8 which are carbon, nitrogen, and oxygen, respectively then correspond to H, He, Li, and Be element 1, 2, 3, and 4. Carbon (6) already corresponds to hydrogen (H), so nitrogen (7) corresponds to H, He, Li, and oxygen (8) corresponds to H, He, Be. This also works because nitrogen (group 15) wants to have stable noble gas electron configuration (group 18) and 18-15=3 meaning it ionizes and oxygen (group 16) wants the same so 18-16=2 meaning it oxidizes O^{2-} . Thus

lithium is 3 protons, and He+H=3 protons for nitrogen (N^{3-}) and oxygen (O^{2-}) is Be-He=2. We have that

$$\frac{1}{6\text{protons}} \cdot \frac{1}{\alpha^2} \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi h}{Gc}} = \frac{1}{6\text{protons}} (6\text{protons} \cdot \text{seconds}) = 1\text{second} = C$$

$$\frac{1}{1\text{protons}} \cdot \frac{1}{\alpha^2} \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi h}{Gc}} = \frac{1}{1\text{protons}} (6\text{protons} \cdot \text{seconds}) = 6\text{seconds} = H$$

We have

Nitrogen

$$\frac{1}{2\text{protons}} \cdot \frac{1}{\alpha^2} \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi h}{Gc}} = \frac{1}{2\text{protons}} (6\text{protons} \cdot \text{seconds}) = 3\text{seconds} = He$$

$$\frac{1}{3\text{protons}} \cdot \frac{1}{\alpha^2} \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi h}{Gc}} = \frac{1}{3\text{protons}} (6\text{protons} \cdot \text{seconds}) = 2\text{seconds} = Li$$

Oxygen

$$\frac{1}{2\text{protons}} \cdot \frac{1}{\alpha^2} \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi h}{Gc}} = \frac{1}{2\text{protons}} (6\text{protons} \cdot \text{seconds}) = 3\text{seconds} = He$$

$$\frac{1}{4\text{protons}} \cdot \frac{1}{\alpha^2} \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi h}{Gc}} = \frac{1}{4\text{protons}} (6\text{protons} \cdot \text{seconds}) = 1.5\text{second} = Be$$

Thus from equation 9

Nitrogen

$$9) m_p \sqrt{\frac{Gc}{h}} \int_0^t dt = r_A$$

$$N^{3-} = m_p \sqrt{\frac{Gc}{h}} \int_0^t dt = (9.2E - 12m/s) \int_0^{1\text{sec}+2\text{sec}+3\text{sec}} dt$$

$$= 5.52E - 11m$$

Where experimentally

$$NH_3 = r_N + r_H = 5.6E - 11m + 5.3E - 11m = 1.1E - 10m$$

And, theoretically

$$NH_3 = r_H + r_H = 5.52E - 11m + 5.5E - 11m = 1.1E - 10m$$

So we are in agreement.

Oxygen

$$O^{2-} = m_p \sqrt{\frac{Gc}{h}} \int_0^t dt = (9.2E - 12m/s) \int_0^{1sec+1.5sec+3sec} dt$$

$$= 5.06E - 11m$$

Where experimentally

$$H_2O = r_O + r_H = 4.8E - 11m + 5.3E - 11m = 1.01E - 10m$$

And, theoretically

$$H_2O = r_O + r_H = 5.06E - 11m + 5.5E - 11m = 1.056E - 10m$$

So we are in good agreement.

Part 3: The Solar Formulation For The Solution Of The Wave Equation

The Solar Formulation

Our solution of the wave equation for the planets gives the kinetic energy of the Earth from the mass of the Moon orbiting the Earth, but you could formulate based on the Earth orbiting the Sun. In our lunar formulation we had:

$$1. \quad KE_e = \sqrt{3} \frac{R_\odot}{R_m} \cdot \frac{G^2 M_e^2 M_m^3}{2 \hbar_\odot^2}$$

We remember the Moon perfectly eclipses the Sun which is to say

$$2. \quad \frac{R_\odot}{R_m} = \frac{r_e}{r_m}$$

Thus equation 1 becomes

$$3. \quad KE_e = \sqrt{3} \frac{r_e}{r_m} \cdot \frac{G^2 M_e^2 M_m^3}{2 \hbar_\odot^2}$$

The kinetic energy of the Earth is

$$4. \quad KE_e = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{GM_\odot M_e}{r_e}$$

Putting this in equation 3 gives the mass of the Sun:

$$5. \quad M_\odot = \sqrt{3} r_e^2 \cdot \frac{GM_e}{r_m} \cdot \frac{M_m^3}{\hbar_\odot^2}$$

We recognize that the orbital velocity of the Moon is

$$6. \quad v_m^2 = \frac{GM_e}{r_m}$$

So equation 5 becomes

$$7. \quad M_\odot = \sqrt{3} r_e^2 \cdot v_m^2 \cdot \frac{M_m^3}{\hbar_\odot^2}$$

This gives the mass of the Moon is

$$8. \quad M_m^3 = \frac{M_\odot \hbar_\odot^2}{\sqrt{3} r_e^2 v_m^2}$$

Putting this in equation 1 yields

$$9. \quad KE_e = \frac{R_\odot}{R_m} \cdot \frac{G^2 M_e^2 M_\odot}{2 r_e^2 v_m^2}$$

We now multiply through by M_e^2/M_e^2 and we have

$$10. \quad KE_e = \frac{R_\odot}{R_m} \cdot \frac{G^2 M_e^4 M_\odot}{2r_e^2 v_m^2 M_e^2}$$

Thus the Planck constant for the Sun, \hbar_\odot , in this the case the star is the Sun, is angular momentum quantized, the angular momentum we will call L_p , the subscript p for Planck. We have

$$L_p = r_e v_m M_e = r_e v_m M_e = (1.496E11m)(1022m/s)(5.972E24kg) = 9.13E38kg \cdot \frac{m^2}{s}$$

$$L_p^2 = r_e^2 v_m^2 M_e^2 = 7.4483E77J \cdot m^2 \cdot kg = 8.3367E77kg^2 \cdot \frac{m^4}{s^2}$$

We write for the solution of the Earth/Sun system:

$$11. \quad KE_e = \frac{R_\odot}{R_m} \cdot \frac{G^2 M_e^4 M_\odot}{2L_p^2}$$

Let us compare this to that of an atom:

$$12. \quad E = -\frac{Z^2}{n^2} \cdot \frac{k_e^2 e^4 m_e}{2\hbar^2}$$

We notice that in equation 11

$$\frac{Z^2}{n^2} \rightarrow \frac{R_\odot}{R_m}; \quad k_e^2 \rightarrow G^2; \quad e^4 \rightarrow M_e^4; \quad m_e \rightarrow M_\odot; \quad \hbar^2 \rightarrow L_p^2$$

L_p is really \hbar_\odot . We can write 11 as

$$13. \quad KE_e = \frac{R_\odot}{R_m} \cdot \frac{G^2 M_e^4 M_\odot}{2\hbar_\odot^2}$$

We say. $\hbar_\odot = \hbar_\odot/2\pi$. That is

$$\hbar_\odot = 9.13E38J \cdot s$$

$$h_\odot = 2\pi\hbar_\odot = 5.7365E39J \cdot s$$

Let us see how accurate our equation is:

$$KE_e = \frac{R_\odot}{R_m} \cdot \frac{G^2 M_e^4 M_\odot}{2\hbar_\odot^2}$$

$$= \frac{R_{\odot} (6.67408E-11)^2 (5.972E24kg)^4 (1.9891E30kg)}{R_m 2(8.3367E77kg^2 \cdot \frac{m^4}{s^2})}$$

$$= \frac{R_{\odot}}{R_m} (6.759E30J)$$

$$\frac{R_{\odot}}{R_m} = \frac{6.957E8m}{1737400m} = 400.426$$

$$KE_e = 2.70655E33J$$

We have that the kinetic energy of the Earth is

$$KE_{earth} = \frac{1}{2} (5.972E24kg) (30,290m/s)^2 = 2.7396E33J$$

Our equation has an accuracy of

$$\frac{2.70655E33J}{2.7396E33J} = 98.79\%$$

Which is very good.

We call L_p the same \hbar_{\odot} in our solar solution. But we now want our r_n solution for the solar formulation. M_e is the mass of the Earth and M_{\odot} is the mass of the Sun. We have our solution might be

$$14. \quad r_n = \frac{\hbar_{\odot}^2}{GM_e^3} \cdot \frac{R_m}{R_{\odot}}$$

Where \hbar_{\odot} is

$$\hbar_{\odot} = 9.13E38J \cdot s$$

We have

$$15. \quad r_3 = \frac{(9.13E38)^2}{(6.67408E-11)(5.972E24kg)^3} \cdot \frac{1}{400.5986} = 1.4638E11m$$

This has an accuracy of

$$\frac{1.4638E11m}{1.496E11m} 100 = 97.85\%$$

Thus the solutions to the wave equation

$$-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \left[\frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r^2 \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \right) + \frac{1}{r^2 \sin \theta} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \left(\sin \theta \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \right) + \frac{1}{r^2 \sin^2 \theta} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \phi^2} \right] \psi + V(r)\psi = E\psi$$

for the solar formulations are

$$13) \quad KE_e = \frac{R_\odot}{R_m} \cdot \frac{G^2 M_e^4 M_\odot}{2\hbar_\odot^2}$$

$$14) \quad r_n = \frac{\hbar_\odot^2}{GM_e^3} \cdot \frac{R_m}{R_\odot}$$

$$\hbar_\odot = 9.13E38J \cdot s$$

$$h_\odot = 2\pi\hbar_\odot = 5.7365E39J \cdot s$$

Equating The Lunar And Solar Formulations Yield Our 1 Second Base Unit

Let us equate equation 1 with equation 13:

$$1. \quad KE_e = \sqrt{n} \frac{R_\odot}{R_m} \cdot \frac{G^2 M_e^2 M_m^3}{2\hbar_\odot^2}$$

$$13. \quad KE_e = \frac{R_\odot}{R_m} \cdot \frac{G^2 M_e^4 M_\odot}{2\hbar_\odot^2}$$

$$\sqrt{3} \frac{R_\odot}{R_m} \cdot \frac{G^2 M_e^2 M_m^3}{2\hbar_\odot^2} = \frac{R_\odot}{R_m} \cdot \frac{G^2 M_e^4 M_\odot}{2L_p^2}$$

This gives:

$$16. \quad L_p = \sqrt{\frac{M_e^2 M_\odot}{M_m^3 \sqrt{3}}} \cdot \hbar_\odot$$

We remember that

$$\hbar_\odot = (hC)KE_p$$

$$hC = 1second$$

$$C = \frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{1}{\alpha^2 c} \sqrt{\frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{2\pi r_p}{Gm_p^3}}$$

$$\frac{1}{6\alpha^2 m_p} \sqrt{\frac{h4\pi r_p^2}{Gc}} = 1.004996352 \text{seconds}$$

This gives

$$17. \quad r_e v_m M_e = \frac{1}{6\alpha^2} \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} \sqrt{\frac{h4\pi}{Gc}} \cdot \frac{1}{2} M_e v_e^2 \cdot \sqrt{\frac{M_e^2 M_\odot}{M_m^3 \sqrt{3}}}$$

We have

$$18. \quad 2v_m = \frac{v_e^2}{r_e} (1 \text{second}) \sqrt{\frac{M_e^2 M_\odot}{M_m^3 \sqrt{3}}}$$

This equates the orbital velocity of the Moon with the centripetal acceleration of the Earth in terms of one second by way of the mass of the Earth, the mass of the Sun, the mass of the Moon, and the orbital number of the Earth. Let us compute

$$19. \quad \sqrt{\frac{M_e^2 M_\odot}{M_m^3 \sqrt{3}}} = \sqrt{\frac{(5.972E24kg)^2 (1.9891E30kg)}{(7.34763E22kg)^3 (1.732)}} = 321,331.459 \approx 321,331$$

Let us see how well equation 18 works. v_m at aphelion is 966 m/s and $v_e = 29,800 \text{m/s}$. $r_e = 1AU = 1.496E11 \text{m}$. We have

$$2(966 \text{m/s}) = \frac{(29,800 \text{m/s})^2}{1.496E11 \text{m}} (1 \text{sec}) (321,331.459)$$

$$1,907 \text{m/s} = 1,932 \text{m/s}$$

That is an accuracy of

$$\frac{1907}{1932} = 98.7 \%$$

Equation 18 can be written:

$$20. \quad 1 \text{second} = 2r_e \frac{v_m}{v_e^2} \sqrt{\frac{M_m^3 \sqrt{3}}{M_e^2 M_\odot}}$$

From our equation:

$$\frac{1}{6\alpha^2 m_p} \sqrt{\frac{h4\pi r_p^2}{Gc}} = 1.004996352 \text{seconds}$$

We have

$$21. \quad \frac{1}{6\alpha^2} \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} \sqrt{\frac{h4\pi}{Gc}} = 2r_e \frac{v_m}{v_e^2} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{M_m^3 \sqrt{3}}{M_e^2 M_\odot}}$$

Since $2r_e = d_e$, the diameter of the Earth orbit, we have

$$22. \quad \frac{1}{6\alpha^2} \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} \sqrt{\frac{h4\pi}{Gc}} = d_e \frac{v_m}{v_e^2} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{M_m^3 \sqrt{3}}{M_e^2 M_\odot}}$$

And we see the Earth/Moon/Sun system determines the radius and mass of the proton and vice versa. We basically have

$$1second = 2v_m \frac{r_e}{v_e^2} \sqrt{\frac{M_m^3 \sqrt{3}}{M_e^2 M_\odot}}$$

$$1second = \frac{KE_{moon}}{KE_{earth}} EarthDay$$

$$1second = \frac{M_m v_m^2}{M_e v_m^2} EarthDay$$

$$23. \quad 62) \quad EarthDay = \frac{2r_e}{v_m} \sqrt{\frac{M_m}{M_\odot} \sqrt{n}}$$

Where $n = 3$ is the Earth orbital number. We have

$$EarthDay = \frac{2(1.496E11m)}{966m/s} \sqrt{\frac{7.34763E22kg}{1.9891E30kg} 1.732}$$

$$= 7.83436E4seconds$$

EarthDay=(24)(60)(60)=86400 seconds,

$$\frac{7.834E4s}{86,400s} 100 = 90.675 \% \text{ accuracy}$$

This last equation, equation 62, we can use to find the rotation period, or the length of the day, of an earth-like planet in the habitable zone of any star system, so it would be very useful.

We want to turn our attention to equation 20 and write it

$$24. \quad 1second = d_e \frac{v_m}{v_e^2} \sqrt{\frac{M_m^3 \sqrt{3}}{M_e^2 M_\odot}}$$

We see equating solar and lunar formulations for energy yield the base unit of one second.

Equating the lunar and solar solutions for orbitals instead of the for energies, which we just did, we have

$$\frac{2\hbar_\odot^2}{GM_m^3} \cdot \frac{R_\odot}{R_m} \cdot \frac{1}{\sqrt{n}} = \frac{L_p^2}{GM_e^3} \cdot \frac{R_m}{R_\odot}$$

Yields

$$25. \quad \hbar_\odot^2 \frac{M_e^3}{M_m^3} = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} L_p^2 \frac{R_m^2}{R_\odot^2}$$

Where $\sqrt{3}/2 = \cos(\pi/6)$. The accuracy of this is

$$(2.8314E33)^2 \frac{(5.972E24)^3}{(7.34763E22)^3} = (0.866)(9.13E38)^2 \frac{(1737400)^2}{(6.96E8)^2}$$

$$4.29059E72 = 4.5005E72$$

$$\frac{4.29059E72}{4.5005E72} 100 = 95.3 \%$$

Thus the energy equations gave the equation 55:

$$16. \quad L_p = \sqrt{\frac{M_e^2 M_\odot}{M_m^3 \sqrt{3}}} \cdot \hbar_\odot$$

And equating the orbital equations gives

$$26. \quad L_p^2 = \frac{2\sqrt{3}}{3} \cdot \frac{M_e^3 R_\odot^2}{M_m^3 R_m^2} \cdot \hbar_\odot^2$$

These last two yield

$$27. \quad \sqrt{2} \frac{R_\odot}{R_m} \sqrt{\frac{M_e}{M_\odot}} = 1$$

The accuracy is

$$(400.5986) \sqrt{\frac{5.972E24kg}{1.9891E30kg}} = 1$$

$$0.98 = 1$$

Is 98% accuracy. The important thing that comes out of this is our base unit of a second because we see it is also a function lunar, solar, and earth masses.

$$24. \quad 1second = d_e \frac{v_m}{v_e^2} \sqrt{\frac{M_m^3 \sqrt{3}}{M_e^2 M_\odot}}$$

Part 4: Wave Solutions For Jupiter And Saturn

Solutions For Jupiter And Saturn

We have the solution for the Bohr hydrogen atom is

$$1 \quad E = - \frac{Z^2(k_e e^2)^2 m_e}{2\hbar^2 n^2}$$

Z is the atomic number, the number of protons orbited, but for our system it is 1, because one body is orbited. n is the orbit number, which we will deal with later. We have our solution for the Earth/Moon/Sun system is

$$2 \quad E = \frac{G^2 M^2 m^3}{2h_{\odot}^2 n^2}$$

Let $M = M_e$ is the earth mass, $m = M_m$ is the lunar mass, and $h_{\odot} = 2.8314E33J \cdot s$ is our Planck constant for the Earth/Moon/Sun system. We compute equation 2:

$$E = \frac{(6.67408E-11)^2(5.972E24kg)^2(7.347673E22kg)^3}{2(2.8314E33)^2 n^2} =$$

$$\frac{3.93E30Joules}{n^2}$$

The kinetic energy of the Earth is

$$KE_e = \frac{1}{2}(5.972E24kg)(30,290m/s)^2 = 2.7396E33J$$

This is $1/n^2 = 697$

The Moon perfectly eclipses the Sun which means as seen from the Earth the Moon appears to be the same size as the Sun. This is because

$$3 \quad \frac{r_e}{r_m} \approx \frac{R_{\odot}}{R_m}$$

Where r_e is the Earth orbital distance, r_m is the Moon's orbital distance, R_{\odot} is the Sun's radius, and R_m is the Moon's radius. This is because though the Moon is 400 times further from the Sun than it is from the Earth, the Sun is 400 times larger than the Moon. That is

$$\frac{6.96E8m}{1737400m} = 400.5986$$

Thus

$$4 \quad \frac{R_{\odot}}{R_m} = 400$$

We find the quantum mechanical solution to the Earth/Moon/System is

$$5 \quad E = \sqrt{n} \frac{R_{\odot}}{R_m} \cdot \frac{G^2 M^2 m^3}{2h_{\odot}^2}$$

$n = 3$ for Earth orbit (Third Planet).

$$\sqrt{3}(400.5986)(3.93E30J) = 2.7268585E33J$$

$$\frac{2.7268585E33}{2.7396E33} = 99.5 \%$$

We see the solar Planck constant we developed works in solving the Schrödinger wave equation for the Earth/Moon/Sun system. My belief as to why this was never done is that it had to be realized that the solution of the Earth kinetic energy around the Sun as a quantum mechanical state is based on the Moon around the Earth.

Now we want to find what the wave equation solutions are for Jupiter and Saturn because they significantly carry the majority of the mass of the solar system and thus should embody most clearly the dynamics of the wave solution to the Solar System.

I find that as we cross the asteroid belt leaving behind the terrestrial planets, which are solid, and go to the gas giants and ice giants, the atomic number is no longer squared and the square root of the the orbital number moves from the numerator to the denominator. I believe this is because the solar system here should be modeled in two parts, just as it is in theories of solar system formation because there is a force other than just gravity of the Sun at work, which is the radiation pressure of the Sun, which is what separates it into two parts, the terrestrial planets on this side of the asteroid belt and the giants on the other side of the asteroid belt. The effect the radiation pressure has is to blow the lighter elements out beyond the asteroid belt when the solar system forms, which are gases such as hydrogen and helium, while the heavier elements are too heavy to be blown out from the inside of the asteroid belt, allowing for the formation of the terrestrial planets Venus, Earth, and Mars. The result is that our equation has the atomic number of the heavier metals such as calcium for the Earth, while the equation for the giants has the atomic numbers of the gasses. We write for these planets

$$6 \quad E = \frac{Z}{\sqrt{n}} \frac{G^2 M^2 m^3}{2\hbar_{\odot}^2}$$

So, for Jupiter we have (And again using the maximum orbital velocity which is at perihelion):

$$KE_j = \frac{1}{2}(1.89813E27kg)(13720m/s)^2 = 1.7865E35J$$

$$E = \frac{Z_H}{\sqrt{5}} \frac{(6.67408E-11)^2(1.89813E27kg)^2(7.347673E22kg)^3}{2(2.8314E33)^2}$$

$$E = \frac{Z_H}{\sqrt{5}}(3.971E35J) = Z_H(1.776E35J)$$

$$Z_H = \frac{1.7865E35J}{1.776E35J} = 1.006 \text{ protons} \approx 1.0 \text{ protons} = \text{hydrogen}(H)$$

Jupiter is mostly composed of hydrogen gas, and secondly helium gas, so it is appropriate that $Z = Z_H$.

Our equation for Jupiter is

$$7 \quad E = \frac{Z_H}{\sqrt{5}} \frac{G^2 M_j^2 M_m^3}{2 \hbar_{\odot}^2}$$

Where Z_H is the atomic number of hydrogen which is 1 proton, and $\sqrt{n} = \sqrt{5}$ for the orbital number of Jupiter, $n = 5$. Now we move on to Saturn...

$$KE_S = \frac{1}{2} (5.683E26kg)(10140m/s)^2 = 2.92E34J$$

$$E = \frac{Z}{\sqrt{6}} \frac{(6.67408E-11)^2 (5.683E26kg)^2 (7.347673E22)^3}{2(2.8314E33)^2}$$

$$= \frac{Z}{2.45} (3.5588E34J) = Z(1.45259E34J)$$

$$Z(1.45259E34J) = (2.92E34J)$$

$$Z = 2 \text{ protons} = \text{Helium}(He)$$

The equation for Saturn is then

$$8 \quad E = \frac{Z_{He}}{\sqrt{6}} \frac{G^2 M_s^2 M_m^3}{2 \hbar_{\odot}^2}$$

It makes sense that Saturn would use Helium in the equation because Saturn is the next planet after Jupiter and Jupiter uses hydrogen, and helium is the next element after hydrogen. As well, just like Jupiter, Saturn is primarily composed of hydrogen and helium gas.

Our equation in this paper for the Earth orbit does not depend on the Moon's distance from the Earth, only its mass. The Moon slows the Earth rotation and this in turn expands the Moon's orbit, so it is getting larger, the Earth loses energy to the Moon. The Earth day gets longer by 0.0067 hours per million years, and the Moon's orbit gets 3.78 cm larger per year. It is believed the Moon came from a chunk knocked off the Earth from a collision with a Mars sized protoplanet. At the time that the Moon formed it was about 4 Earth radii distant 4.5 billion years ago. After 100 million years the Moon became tidally locked making its rotation period equal to its orbital period keeping one face always towards the Earth. After 500 million years the Moon was orbiting at about 20 Earth radii. It is believed that during the period of heavy bombardment in a chaotic early solar system about 4.1 to 3.8 billion years ago a large object did a close pass pulling the Moon further changing its orbit giving it its 5 degree offset from the Earth's equator. Our wave equation solution may only use the Moon's mass but the equation for

kinetic energy of the Moon to kinetic energy of the Earth times the Earth Day equal to about one second:

$$\frac{KE_{moon}}{KE_{earth}}(EarthDay) = 1.08seconds$$

Which we connect with the equation where the proton gives one second

$$\frac{1}{6\alpha^2 m_p} \sqrt{\frac{h4\pi r_p^2}{Gc}} = 1.004996354seconds$$

This holds for when the Moon was at a distance from the Earth such that it appears the same size as the Sun, which means:

$$\frac{r_{planet}}{r_{moon}} \approx \frac{R_{star}}{R_{moon}}$$

Which is when the two equations above for one second connect to our wave equation solution to the Earth

$$KE_e = \sqrt{n} \frac{R_{\odot}}{R_m} \cdot \frac{G^2 M_e^2 M_m^3}{2\hbar_{\odot}^2}$$

$$\text{Because } \frac{R_{star}}{R_{moon}} = \frac{R_{\odot}}{R_m}.$$

The Moon at its inclination to the Earth in its orbit makes life possible here because it holds the Earth at its tilt to its orbit around the Sun allowing for the seasons so the Earth doesn't get too extremely hot or too extremely cold. We see the Moon may be there for a reason.

Part 5: Modeling Habitable Star Systems

Modeling Habitable Star Systems

We want to solve a habitable planetary system in general and apply it to another star system. We must include the solution of its moon as well, because the Moon of the Earth makes life optimally possible. However, our Moon is counter-intuitive, it breaks all of the rules of the other moons in our solar system. One is it has a low mass for its size. It has been said that it could be hollow. Even suggested that it is a hollow-spacecraft put there to make life as we know it possible. In our quantum theory for the solar system, we may have discovered the science of the engineers who may have made the Moon, and we are possibly applying their science here. Our quantum theory for the solar system also has a solar solution as compared to a lunar solution, so it works for star systems in general.

The perfect star system to use for our purposes here would be Tau Ceti. Tau Ceti is a star spectrally similar to the Sun and the closest of such a G-class star, at about 12 light years distant. Its mass is 78% of the Sun's. Its mass is

$$M_s = 0.783 + / - 0.012M_{\odot}$$

Its radius is:

$$R_s = 0.793 + / - 0.004R_{\odot}$$

And its luminosity is

$$L_s = 0.488 + / - 0.0010L_{\odot}$$

It has several unconfirmed planets with one potentially in the habitable zone. It has been the subject of science fiction literature. It is in the constellation Cetus. From Tau Ceti the Earth would be seen to be in the northern hemisphere constellation Bootes with an apparent magnitude of 2.6. It is spectral class G8 V where our Sun is G2 V.

For the luminosity of a main sequence star we only need to know the mass of the star to get its luminosity:

$$1 \quad L = M^{3.5}$$

This holds in solar masses and solar luminosities. The habitable zone of a star is given by luminosity. If the star is 100 times brighter than our Sun, then the habitable zone is 10 times further than the Earth is from the Sun by the inverse square law.

$$2 \quad r_p = \sqrt{L_s}$$

In astronomical units and solar luminosities. From r_p we can get the orbital period in Earth years:

$$3 \quad T_p^2 = r_p^3$$

We can get the radius of the Moon of the planet if we know the mass of the planet, M_e :

$$4 \quad \sqrt{2} \frac{R_{\odot}}{R_m} \sqrt{\frac{M_e}{M_{\odot}}} = 1$$

We want the mass of the Earth from the mass of the Sun. We would guess we can get it from the mass of the Sun, the size of the Sun, and the base 60 sexagesimal system upon which we have found everything is based. I find the relationship exists for the Earth:

$$5 \quad M_e = \frac{5}{6^2} M_{\odot} \frac{R_{\odot}^2}{r_e^2}$$

(36)(5)=180=360/2 and 360/6=60 is base 60 sexagesimal. This gives

$$M_e = 0.13889(1.9891E30kg) \frac{6.96E8m^2}{1.496E11m^2} = 5.979748E24kg$$

This is an accuracy of

$$\frac{5.972E24}{5.979748E24} 100 = 99.87 \%$$

We can get the orbital distance of the planet's Moon from the planet:

$$6 \quad \frac{r_{planet}}{r_{moon}} \approx \frac{R_{star}}{R_{moon}}$$

Once we have that we can get the radius of the Moon of the planet

$$7 \quad \sqrt{2} \frac{R_{\odot}}{R_m} \sqrt{\frac{M_e}{M_{\odot}}} = 1$$

Now we can get the rotation period of the planet, its length of day:

$$8 \quad EarthDay = \frac{2r_e}{v_m} \sqrt{\frac{M_m}{M_{\odot}}} \sqrt{3}$$

Because the orbital velocity of the planet's Moon is

$$9 \quad v_m = \sqrt{\frac{GM_e}{r_m}}$$

We can use the the delocalization time get the moon's mass, which is 1/2 the planet's year, with

$$10 \quad \tau = \frac{m_{moon}(2r_{moon})^2}{\hbar_s} \quad , \quad \text{See Appendix 1}$$

And the whole system is solved. Let us see how the theoretical luminosity appears with that measured with equation 8.1:

$$L_s = M_s^{3.5} = 0.783^{3.5} = 0.425L_{\odot}$$

It is close to the $0.448L_{\odot}$ measured. The equation for predicting is approximate as the actual values can vary a little with things like metallicity of the stars. Tau Ceti has low metallicity compared to our Sun.

Let's find the orbital distance of the habitable planet if it exists with equation 2:

$$r_p = \sqrt{0.488} = 0.69857AU = (0.6986AU)(1.496E11m/AU) = 1.045E11meters$$

Let's find the orbital period of the habitable planet (It's year) with equation 3:

$$T_p^2 = r_p^3, \quad T_p^2 = (0.69867AU)^3$$

$$T_p = 0.584years(365.25days)((24hrs)(60min)(60sec) = 1849638seconds$$

$$=(0.584)(365.25days) = 213.306days$$

Let's get the mass of the habitable planet from equation 5:

$$M_p = \frac{5}{36} M_s \frac{R_s^2}{r_p^2}$$

$$M_s = (0.783)(1.9891E30kg) = 1.5575E30kg$$

$$R_s = (0.793)(6.96E8m) = 5.52E8m$$

$$M_p = \frac{5}{36}(1.5575E30kg) \frac{(5.52E8m)^2}{(1.045E11m)^2} = 6.036E24kg$$

$$= \frac{6.036E24}{5.972E24} = 1.0107EarthMasses$$

Which is good because the planet, if it exists, is thought to be larger than the Earth. Let's get the radius of its moon from equation 4:

$$R_m = \sqrt{2}R_s \sqrt{\frac{M_p}{M_s}}$$

$$= \sqrt{2}(5.52E8m) \sqrt{\frac{(6.036E24kg)}{(1.5575E30kg)}} = 1.53656E6m = \frac{1.53656E6m}{1.7374E6m} = 0.8844LunarRadii$$

Let's see at what distance it orbits the planet with equation 6:

$$r_{moon} = r_{planet} \frac{R_{moon}}{R_{star}} = (1.045E11m) \frac{1.53656E6m}{5.52E8m} = 2.91E8m$$

$$= \frac{2.91E8m}{3.84E8m} = 0.7578 \text{ Lunar Orbital Radii}$$

Let's get the orbital velocity of this moon with equation 9:

$$v_m = \sqrt{\frac{GM_p}{r_m}} = \sqrt{\frac{(6.67408E-11)(6.0636E24kg)}{2.91E8m}} = 1,176.6m/s$$

So the orbital period of the moon is:

$$T_m = \frac{2\pi r_m}{v_m} = \frac{2\pi(.91E8m)}{1,176.6m/s} = 1.554E6seconds$$

$$= (1.554E6s) \frac{min}{60sec} \frac{hour}{60min} \frac{day}{24hours} = 17.987days$$

Compared to that of the Earth which is 27.3 days for the sidereal month and is a 29.53day lunar month. The Moon of Tau Ceti would have a slightly longer lunar month, too. Now we can determine the rotation period of the planet which would be its day:

We get the mass of the moon from equation 10:

$$M_m = \frac{\hbar_s \tau}{4r_m^2} = \frac{(2.8314E33J \cdot s)(0.5)(18429638s)}{4(2.91E8m)^2} = 7.7E22kg$$

$$= \frac{7.7E22kg}{7.34763E22kg} = 1.048 \text{ Earth Moons}$$

So the rotation period of the planet (Its Day) is from equation 8:

$$PlanetDay = \frac{2r_p}{v_m} \sqrt{\frac{M_m}{M_s}} \sqrt{3}$$

$$= \frac{2(1.045E11m)}{1,176.6m/s} \sqrt{\frac{7.7E22kg}{1.5575E30kg}} = 39495.61seconds = 658.26min = 10.971hours$$

$$= \frac{10.971}{24hours} = 0.457 \text{ Earth Days}$$

If the moon of Tau Ceti is to perfectly eclipse its star, like our Moon does with the Sun, to let its inhabitants know that they are there for reason, and so as to theoretically be a condition for optimizing life, then we have the following should hold:

$$\frac{r_{planet}}{r_{moon}} \approx \frac{R_{star}}{R_{moon}}$$

We have

$$\frac{1.045E11m}{2.91E8m} = \frac{5.52E8m}{1.53656E6m}$$

$$359 = 359$$

And it does hold. For the Earth/Moon/Sun system we get

$$400 = 400$$

For the Tau Ceti system the 359 is close to 360, which is a convenient amount of degrees into which divide a circle, like we did. We see the Tau Cetians might do the same, because like us they might choose the base 60 sexagesimal system of counting, and this 360 might influence the way the inhabitants of a planet orbiting this star would make their calendar. Just like the 365 day year here on Earth corresponds closely to the 360 degrees of a circle. Aside from having here on Earth the degree, we have gradians, of which there are 400 in a circle. They make it very easy for computing right angles to a given angle. They are used more in Europe and in surveying and architecture, though it might have some interesting connection with our 400=400.

The habitable planet of Tau Ceti would orbit its star with a period of 213 days, which would be its year. Its star is about 78% the mass of our Sun, and about 79% its size. Its habitable planet would be a little larger than the Earth, but not much. Its Moon would be about 88% the size of our moon, but a little bit more massive, but not much more massive. It would orbit Tau Ceti once about every 18 days meaning there would be 11.833 months in the Tau Ceti Year, or about 12 months like we have. It would orbit the planet at about three quarters the distance ours does. The day from sunrise to sunrise, or sunset to sunset would be about 11 hours, or close to half the length of our day. This is if Tau Ceti was engineered for life, but it doesn't have to have a planet so optimally designed for life as ours. Our 24 hour day would be better for when entering the realm of doing astronomy, because longer nights mean more complete observations of the universe surrounding us than for the Tau Cetians. It may mean for the conditions for life to be optimal, like here on Earth, the star would have to be as massive as the Sun, to provide a longer year and a longer day. But we see here how the science of engineering planetary systems optimal for life, might be done.

Appendix 1

If we want to prove that our planetary Planck constant is correct, the delocalization time for the Earth should be 6 months using it, the time for the Earth to travel the width of its orbit. We want to solve the Schrödinger wave equation for a wave packet and use the most basic thing we can which is a Gaussian distribution. We want to then substitute for Planck's constant h that is used for quanta and atoms our Planck-type constant \hbar_{\odot} (\hbar bar solar) for the Earth/Moon/Sun system then apply it to predict the delocalization time for the Moon in its orbit with the Earth around the Sun.

We consider a Gaussian wave-packet at $t=0$:

$$\psi(x,0) = A e^{-\frac{x^2}{2d^2}}$$

We say that d is the delocalization length and decompose the wave packet with a Fourier transform:

$$\psi(x,0) = A e^{-\frac{x^2}{2d^2}} = \int \frac{dp}{2\pi\hbar} \phi_p e^{\frac{i}{\hbar} px}$$

ϕ_p is the harmonics of the wave function. We use the identity that gives the integral of a quadratic:

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-\alpha^2 x + \beta x} dx = \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{\alpha}} e^{\frac{\beta^2}{4\alpha}}$$

Solve the equation

$$i\hbar\partial_t\psi(x,t) = \frac{\hat{p}}{2m}\psi(x,t)$$

With the initial condition

$$\psi(x,0) = \int dp \cdot e^{\frac{p^2 d^2}{2\hbar^2}} \cdot e^{-\frac{i}{\hbar} px}$$

A plane wave is the solution:

$$e^{\frac{i}{\hbar}(px - \epsilon(p)t)}$$

$$\text{Where, } \epsilon(p) = \frac{p^2}{2m}$$

The wave-packet evolves with time as

$$\psi(x,t) = \int dp \cdot e^{\frac{p^2 d^2}{2\hbar^2}} \cdot e^{-\frac{i}{\hbar}(px - \frac{p^2}{2m}t)}$$

Calculate the Gaussian integral of dp

$$\alpha^2 = \frac{d^2}{2\hbar^2} + \frac{it}{2m\hbar} \text{ and } \beta = \frac{ix}{\hbar}$$

The solution is:

$$|\psi|^2 = \exp \left[-\frac{x^2}{d^2} \cdot \frac{1}{1 + t^2/\tau^2} \right] \text{ where } \tau = \frac{md^2}{\hbar}$$

d is the delocalization distance, which for instance could be the width of an atom. τ is the delocalization time, the average time for say an electron to traverse the diameter of the atom and even leave it, to delocalize. If we substitute for \hbar our \hbar_{\odot} , and say that the delocalization distance is for the Moon, the width of the Earth orbit, we should get a half a year for the delocalization time, the time for the Moon and Earth to traverse the diameter of their orbit around the Sun. We have

$$\tau = \frac{m_{moon}(2r_{moon})^2}{\hbar_{\odot}}$$

Where m_{moon} is the mass of the Moon, and r_{moon} is the orbital radius of the Moon. We have

$$\tau = 4 \frac{(7.34767E22kg)(3.844E8m)^2}{2.8314E33J \cdot s} = 15338227 \text{ seconds}$$

Now let's compute a half a year...

$$(1/2)(365.25)(24)(60)(60) = 15778800 \text{ seconds}$$

So we see our delocalization time is very close to the half year over which the Earth and Moon travel from one position to the opposite side of the Sun. The closeness is

$$\frac{15338227}{15778800} 100 = 97.2 \%$$

Thus we know our \hbar_{\odot} is accurate, it continues to function in a theoretical framework. The thing about this is that it means we can predict the mass of the Moon from the Earth year. In terms of what we said earlier that the Moon allows for life by creating the seasons, holding the Earth at its tilt to the Sun, so we don't go through extreme heat and cold, this suggests the Moon has a mass that follows from Earth orbit, which is the habitable zone of the Sun, the right distance for water to exist as liquid, and thus could be as it is for a reason, which means life might be part of a physical process throughout the Universe, that it unfolds naturally in the evolution of star systems.

Appendix 2: The Data For Verifying The Equations

$m_p: 1.67262 \times 10^{-27} \text{kg}$ (Proton Mass)

$h: 6.62607 \times 10^{-34} \text{J} \cdot \text{s}$ (Planck Constant)

$r_p: 0.833 \times 10^{-15} \text{m}$ (Proton Radius)

$G: 6.67408 \times 10^{-11} \text{N} \frac{\text{m}^2}{\text{kg}^2}$ (Gravitational Constant)

$c : 299,792,458 \text{m/s}$ (light speed)

$\alpha: 1/137$ (Fine Structure Constant)

$q_p = q_e = 1.6022 \text{E} - 19 \text{coulombs}$

$k_e = 8.988 \text{E}9 \frac{\text{Nm}^2}{\text{C}^2}$

Earth day=(24)(60)(60)=86,400 seconds. Using the Moon's orbital velocity at aphelion, and Earth's orbital velocity at perihelion we have:

$$KE_{moon} = \frac{1}{2}(7.347673 \text{E} 22 \text{kg})(966 \text{m/s})^2 = 3.428 \text{E} 28 \text{J}$$

$$KE_{earth} = \frac{1}{2}(5.972 \text{E} 24 \text{kg})(30,290 \text{m/s})^2 = 2.7396 \text{E} 33 \text{J}$$

The Author

